

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASÍDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍN INTEGRACIYASÍ» atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

ASSESSMENT OF THE RESOURCE POTENTIAL OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF AGRICULTURE

Umarova A.E.,
assistant teacher. NGPI(Nukus).
(for example from the point of view of
agriculture)
E-mail: aysuluumarova1991@gmail.com

Abstract: In the scientific article discusses the rational use of natural and economic potential in the context of improving the territorial organization of production economic areas Aral Sea region.

Keywords: potential, intensification, specialization, acceleration, efficiency irrigation systems, resource, innovation, Agro-industrial complex.

Umarova A.E Priaraliskiy region is part of Aralokaspiyskoy lowlands, occupying extensive delta area yard Amudarii, length beside 500 km. In this natural-economic region are located Karakalpakstan and Horezmskaya area Uzbekistan, Tashauzskaya area Turkmenistan, as well as crosses the borders Mangistauskoy, Aktyubinskoy and Kyzylordinskoy area Kazakhstan. The Territory is located in zone desert temperate zone, natural condition is characterized by cutting continental. Here concentrated more than 20 % ground fund middle english republics. From these lands on segment, the Republics Karakalpakstan to happen to 16,6 mln. ga.. However, tap in large scale Amudariinskoy water on irrigation in upper and at the average his(its) current, mastering natural resource Priaraliskogo region becomes very difficult. All this requires in the first place all-round study resource potential with standpoint of the agriculture, which is composed of from land, water, agroclimate and others resource.

The General area arable-suitable lands only Karakalpakstana forms more than 2 mln. ga. However, degree actual masteringhis(its) irrigated forms only 2,5%. All this confirms presence greater non-exempt resource in absolute, so and in relative calculus. Together with that necessary to note that resource potential of the region, in particular irrigated ploughed field provided by irrigation network, from for deteriorations land reclamation conditions of the lands засолены to a considerable extent. The Group on land reclamation to condition of the irrigated lands, as main potential resource of the agrarian sector shows that only 20,6% their area are referred to the best category of the lands and 33,8% lands pertains weakly, 34,3% midwestern, but 11,3% to powerfully i.e. pertains the showing little profit for irrigated husbandries. All this vastly complicates increasing to efficiency of the irrigated lands

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and requires the enormous amount to investments, involvement them in agricultural turn.

The Greater reserves of the irrigated lands stir, basically, in zone of the influence Tahiatashskogo hydrodynamics on riverbed channel r. Amudarii mainly, as well as in zone influence irrigation systems. Production use their requires the large hydrometer of the work, in particular construction collector-drainage to network. What the practice witnesses, use collector-drainage to network the most efficient measure. As example possible to show work cotton grower facilities Horezmskoy area, residing in soil-land reclamation attitude in one zone with Karakalpakstanom. Here specific extent collector-drainage to network on disadvantage lands bring before 40-45 м/га while in Republic Karakalpakstan before 23-27 м/га, but in seaside part else less. This obviously it is not enough for improvement land reclamation conditions of the irrigated lands. In this connection for increasing of the cost-performance of the irrigated lands, was reasonable, will pay earnest heed on improvement structured-management base of the agrarian sector by by stimulations scientifically motivated methods of the management.

The Facility of the agriculture according to with methods designed by akad. Medetullaevym ZH, are reduced to estimation of the land as material base agricultural production. This is connected with that that in productivity of the land is synthesized favourable climatic, soil, water, hydrology, land reclamation and the other conditions, forming united on its structure, complex ambience grow agricultural cultures. Thereby, in practice estimation to productivity of the land became the object of the study ensemble sciences. Each of these branch sciences researches the dependency to productivity of the land on determined, inherent him factor. So, for instance geographers for base of productivity use the factor to supplies of the land termal resource, solar illumination, atmospheric влагой; the botanists - productivity natural herbivorous; but economists do the preferences on amounts of the investments and etc. Thereby, one of them in base of the estimation of the land puts the natural signs, the other group volume investment ambience. As a result exists the trend of the gradual approach the estimation to practical request production, use her(it) for integer of the accomodation of the branches of the agriculture. Such direction of the development of the methods of the choice of the object for estimation of the land in purpose agricultural production is natural, but nowhere near not last. This also points to practicability of the development of the methods of the firm development of the agrarian sector with provision for undertaking quantitative and qualitative estimation

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resource potential. In this plan, in base of the estimation level to intensities of the use the irrigated lands, is accepted potential productivity irrigated to ploughed fields. She is founded on difference between reached and potential level to productivity irrigated to ploughed fields. Her(its) possible define on the following formula:

$$E e = VD_2 : OZ_2 - VD_1 : OZ_1,$$

where, Ee-a cost-performance of the mastering to potential product on intensities of the use the land, bags/ ga VD_2 -a gross incom APK region on the end of the forecasted period, thous. bags VD_1 -a gross incom APK region on begin forecasted period, thous. bags OZ_2 - irrigated land on the end of the forecasted period, thous. ga OZ_1 - irrigated land on begin forecasted period, thous. ga.

Coming from this positions, is determined level of the return land-water resource. The Calculations are indicative of that that expansion of the irrigated areas in south region becomes not only possible, but also economic expedient.

The Main factor, defining possibility of the mastering to potential productivity land and termal resource aryan zones, is presence of irrigation water. As is well known, in our condition irrigation water in over and over again less, than facility arable lands. So lawful concept about that that difference to productivity between natural pasture and irrigated husbandry in condition aryan zones is a factor, defining efficiency of irrigation water.

For determination of productivity of irrigation water, necessary to bear in mind potential productivity irrigated ploughed fields with provision for termal resource, land reclamation of the condition of the lands and standards of water on unit of the ploughed fields. Potential productivity (the economic possible level) of the unit of irrigation water corresponds to the amount of the cost main and additional product, done on amount of water. Herewith, is here accepted in calculation potential productivity 1m³ water used in cotton growing, in 390,4 bags to gross output. In natural factor this corresponds to 0,333 kg. pat-product in its raw state. Follows to take into account that potential productivity of irrigation water is greatly changed on type of the agricultural cultures. With provision for this, according to afore-cited rate, 1834,3 m³/ga. and at gross output of the cotton plant on 1 ga. 1009400 bags and realization price of the centner of the pat 49000 bags forms 390,4 bags:

$$П_{\text{e1}} = \frac{20,6\text{ц} / \text{га.хлопка} - 2\text{ц} / \text{га.сум}}{1834,3\text{м}^3 + 700\text{м}^3} = \frac{1009400\text{сум} / \text{га.} - 20000\text{сум} / \text{га.}}{2534,3\text{м}^3} = 390,4\text{сум} / \text{м}^3;$$

Thereby, each m³ water, under high level agronomisand use her(it) on irrigation of the cotton plant will at the average provide the increase to gross output in amount

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390,4 bags. Besides, to account of increasing KPD irrigation systems, including inwardly irrigation network, possible enlarge the efficient volume of irrigation water, on 50-55%.

In this sense introduces important, increasing KPD irrigation systems, selecting the agricultural cultures to termal condition lower reached Amudarii with reference to, as well as define the productivity of the agricultural cultures on hectare of the land not only, but also on crew's quarters, consumed on flight of water.

For determination of the cost-performance of the agrarian sector Priaraliskogo region, in particular Karakalpakstana, we, first of all, shall value her(it) on suplies efficient temperature, so required for development and bear fruit heat of the plants.

The Feature of the climate with standpoint of the agriculture shows that under other equal agronomist condition exists the certain interdependence between length vegetarian period, amount of the efficient temperature and productivity of the agricultural cultures. So, between facilities located on extreme south and north point cotton grower, there are differences in length vegetarian period with the temperature above $+10^{\circ}\text{C}$ (in Turtkule 205 days, in Kungrade 186 days), in amount of the efficient temperature (above $+10^{\circ}\text{C}$) in Turtkule -2258°C , in Kungrade -1914°C . Thereby, study result grow cotton plant in experimental facilities shows that, as from south region, reduction to length вегетационного period with the temperature above $+10^{\circ}\text{C}$ on 1 day brings about reduction of the potential productivity of the cotton plant on 1 centner approximately. So displacement much (except facilities) of the sowing areas of the cotton plant with North on South that was reasonable and with standpoint state interest As a result, in condition South region by by increasing to productivities 27,9 c with hectare, annual production of the pat product in its raw state can reach 192,5 thous. tons, in central and in north region, with provision for reductions of the sowing of the cotton plant on 35%-40% possible get 116,1 thous. tons of the pat at productivities 22,6 c with hectare. This in condition north region will bring about expansion of the sowing areas other corn cultures. Thereby, involvement in agric turn unused reserve production by by deepening the intensive methods of the introduction production, as well as with provision for optimization of the branch structure of the agrarian sector, possible in addition get annually- 0,394 mln. tons grain, 0,297 - 0,301 mln. tons of the pat-product in its raw state. In conclusion possible to note that main essence of the study resource potential of the region, is attraction intellectual-dissidence resource for mastering resource potential with standpoint of the agriculture, which will provide the coordinations a work within the

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framework of region construction large hydrometer-hydrophobia object promoting firm development agricultural production.

LITERATURE:

1. Медетуллаев ZH.M. Zemelinyy potential Karakalpakstana object complex study. The Herald KGU im. Berdaha 4-5 2009 p. 38-40.
2. Umarov E. K.- Economy-geographical aspects of the rational use water resource in irrigated husbandry of the Republic Karakalpakstan// Herald TREASURY im. Scarlet -Farabi, Series geographical- 2(19), Almaty 2004.
3. The Statistical yearbook region Uzbekistan. Tashkent – 2010,2015,2020.